

Policy Brief no. 5

Reducing Climate Risks through Just Transition Policies

September 2025

Funded by European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094551

Key messages

- **Persistent energy poverty and multidimensional climate risks** generate cumulative disadvantages that vary substantially across European regions, creating “vulnerability traps” where households struggle to escape overlapping risks.
- **Multi-sectorial policies that combine improvements in income, housing, energy, health, and social protections consistently outperform single-sector measures**, demonstrating that comprehensive approaches are needed rather than isolated interventions.
- **Income protection, housing quality, and renovation emerge as central policy levers for reducing climate vulnerabilities**, with household income explaining much of the observed variation. These factors should be seen as core but not sufficient on their own.
- **Targeted measures are more effective in reaching those in vulnerable situations**, but they should be embedded within a universal framework to guarantee fairness and avoid exclusion.

Background & Context

The Imperative of Leaving No One Behind

The transition towards climate neutrality represents a profound societal transformation that affects different segments of society in unequal ways. While the urgency of achieving net zero emissions is clear, the pathway to decarbonisation produces varied impacts across regions, communities, and social groups. The closure of fossil fuel facilities, the expansion of renewable energy, and the broader restructuring of economies generate uneven outcomes that risk leaving certain populations behind. Workers in traditional energy sectors face job displacement, communities dependent on carbon-intensive industries confront economic uncertainty, and households experience rising costs, particularly in energy and transport. These disparities underscore the need for deliberate action to guarantee that the benefits of climate action are maximised while adverse consequences are minimised.

The concept of an inclusive climate transition captures this reality by recognising that both the impacts of climate change and the effects of mitigation policies are unevenly distributed. Approaching climate

policy through the lens of equity means addressing multiple dimensions of inequality, vulnerability, and opportunity. The goal extends beyond environmental outcomes to encompass social inclusion and the fair distribution of costs and benefits throughout the transformation process.

Social justice plays a central role in this agenda. It is first and foremost an ethical imperative: certain groups and regions contribute least to historical emissions yet face the most severe consequences, while intergenerational justice demands that today's decisions do not shift disproportionate costs onto younger and future populations. But social justice is also a pragmatic condition for the political and social feasibility of ambitious climate action. Without fairness, policies are unlikely to gain lasting public support, and resistance can delay or derail essential measures. In this sense, equity is not an optional add-on but a foundational requirement for effective and sustainable climate governance.

Justice in climate policy has multiple dimensions. Distributional justice requires acknowledging and redressing disproportionate impacts on vulnerable

communities and ensuring that access to affordable energy, green finance, and sustainable alternatives does not become a new source of exclusion. Historical justice highlights the responsibility of wealthier countries that have been major emitters, while procedural justice stresses the importance of meaningful participation. Involving workers, businesses, and communities in negotiation, consultation, and information-sharing ensures that policies respond to real needs and foster legitimacy. This inclusive approach recognises diverse local circumstances and encourages coordination across scales and sectors. Historical experience reinforces these lessons. Environmental policies that failed to account for social consequences have often struggled with implementation, whereas those designed with fairness in mind have proven more durable. Embedding social justice at the heart of climate strategies therefore increases both their ethical coherence and their political viability. In sum, the transition to climate neutrality cannot be understood solely as a technical or environmental project. Its success depends on ensuring that no person and no place is left behind, and on recognising that equity is at once a moral obligation and a condition of feasibility. A truly inclusive transition requires policies that not only reduce emissions but also confront existing inequalities, expand opportunities, and strengthen the social contract on which ambitious climate action ultimately depends.

Main Policy Tools in the European Union

The EU has built a policy framework that combines ambitious climate targets with attention to social equity and regional balance. Achieving climate neutrality by 2050 requires managing social and economic transitions carefully to maintain support and ensure fair outcomes.

The **European Green Deal** (2019) is the EU's overarching strategy, aiming for net-zero emissions by 2050 while decoupling growth from resource use and ensuring no person or place is left behind. It covers sectors from energy and transport to agriculture and industry, backed by major funding— one-third of the €1.8 trillion EU budget and NextGenerationEU. Key goals include cutting emissions by 55% by 2030 (vs. 1990 levels) and planting 3 billion trees by 2030.

The **Just Transition Fund** (2021–2027), part of the EU's Cohesion Policy, supports regions most affected by the shift from carbon-intensive activities. It promotes place-based solutions tailored to local needs and coordinates action across governments and companies.

The **Social Climate Fund** addresses the social impacts of the new emissions trading system for buildings and transport (ETS2). It targets vulnerable households facing energy or transport poverty through efficiency renovations, clean heating, sustainable transport, and optional income support.

Together, these three instruments illustrate the EU's integrated approach: tackling climate goals while safeguarding inclusion and regional cohesion across multiple scales.

SPES Evidence

The SPES project recognizes that rising inequalities, persistent multidimensional poverty, and climate change represent alarming trends facing societies today, often attributed to policy decisions that focus too narrowly on GDP growth as the only measure of prosperity. Among others, SPES research focuses on identifying socioeconomic and demographic groups vulnerable to shocks directly and indirectly linked to climate change, including impacts from increasing energy prices. SPES research in this area employs empirical analysis to map vulnerabilities and inform policy approaches that ensure the sustainability transition does not disproportionately burden vulnerable populations. According to the evidence, patterns of vulnerability manifest both across regions (e.g., the North–South divide) and within regions (unequal distribution across socioeconomic groups), requiring multi-level responses.

Energy Poverty and Persistent Vulnerabilities Across Europe

EU-SILC data (2017–2020) reveal marked disparities in energy poverty across 29 countries (Krstić et al., 2024). The Energy Poverty Index (EPI), combining heating difficulties, bill arrears, and poor housing

conditions, ranges from 0.02 in Norway to 0.21 in Bulgaria. Highest levels occur in Bulgaria, Lithuania, Portugal, and Greece; lowest in Northern Europe. A clear North–South divide emerges, with Southern and Eastern countries showing values six times larger than Northern ones. Housing problems drive energy poverty most strongly across Europe.

Persistence is especially concerning. In Bulgaria, 24% of households remain energy poor across several years, compared to less than 1% in Nordic countries. This “energy poverty trap” reflects how initial deprivation strongly predicts continued energy insecurity.

Demographic and Socioeconomic Determinants of Energy Vulnerability

Regression analysis identifies consistent drivers of energy poverty (Krstić et al., 2024). Larger household size, low education, unemployment, and health-related inactivity all raise risk. Income is strongly protective everywhere, with effects ranging from -0.01 in Switzerland to -0.16 in Greece. Interestingly, households with elderly members (65+) are less likely to be energy poor, particularly in Belgium and the Netherlands.

Housing conditions matter greatly.

Inadequate natural lighting increases the risk from 8% in Finland to 42% in Italy. Renters face higher probability of energy poverty than homeowners, by 4% in Germany and Latvia up to 15% in Italy and Portugal. In Bulgaria and Lithuania, an additional room lowers the likelihood by about three percentage points.

Multidimensional Climate-Related Vulnerabilities

Beyond energy poverty, cumulative risks reveal layered vulnerabilities (Palencia-Esteban et al., 2024). The framework integrates four risk dimensions—energy and transport poverty, cardiovascular problems, and respiratory issues—together with three socioeconomic amplifiers.

Geographically, Mediterranean and Eastern Europe, particularly Bulgaria, show highest average risk. Cardiovascular problems, poverty, and energy and transport insecurity consistently dominate. Distributional patterns differ: in Eastern Europe and Italy, risks are widespread but evenly distributed, suggesting fairness. By contrast, in Cyprus, Ireland, Belgium, and Austria, risks cluster among specific groups, creating inequality and dependence across dimensions

Projected Future Vulnerabilities

Looking forward, projections under alternative climate scenarios (Palencia-Esteban & Valentini, 2025) suggest energy and transport poverty could increase by up to 20% in vulnerable regions by 2050. In relative terms, affected population shares could double or even triple in some areas. Socioeconomic conditions change only modestly—mainly through population aging—but fuel-related vulnerabilities rise sharply, signaling a widening risk landscape.

Evidence demonstrates that climate-related vulnerabilities are not randomly distributed.

They concentrate in specific groups, persist over time, and are expected to intensify without coordinated action. Energy poverty illustrates both high regional disparities and the danger of long-term entrapment. Broader analyses show cumulative risks that overlap and reinforce each other, with certain regions facing both high exposure and unequal distribution.

The evidence shows that climate-related risks are cumulative, persistent, and unevenly distributed, affecting vulnerable groups disproportionately. Addressing these challenges requires a framework that connects social protection, employment, and decarbonisation in an integrated way.

Several existing frameworks – including the ILO Just Transition guidelines and 2023 declaration, Raworth’s Doughnut Economics, Yunus’s “Three Zeros”, the JRC framework on sustainable and inclusive wellbeing, among others – insist on the interdependence between poverty reduction, decent work, and climate neutrality as mutually reinforcing goals when pursued together.

This perspective is fundamental for the current European context. As the SPES evidence demonstrates, households at risk of energy poverty need protection from rising costs, workers facing transition require access to new opportunities, and ambitious decarbonisation must remain socially legitimate

Taken together, these goals underscore the importance of policies that are multidimensional by design. The following recommendations build directly on this insight, translating principles into actionable directions for the European policy context.

Policy recommendations

01.

Develop **Comprehensive, Multi-Instrument Policy Packages.**

Isolated policy interventions fail to address the complex, multidimensional nature of energy poverty and climate transition challenges. Evidence shows that combining decarbonization policies with high subsidy rates and targeted support reduces both consumption and poverty. During recent energy crises, strategies that combined price measures with household transfers proved more effective than transfers alone. National examples such as Spain's multi-category approach successfully combined immediate relief with structural improvements, while others coordinated energy efficiency support with landlord-tenant agreements. In contrast, minimal approaches limited to basic financial aid without consumer protections failed to address multidimensional vulnerability (Kyprianou et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Alvarez et al., 2021).

To make such comprehensive packages effective, their design must ensure that short-term relief measures are consistently linked with long-term structural reforms. This requires coordination across sectors—such as housing, energy, transport, and social protection—so that interventions are not delivered in isolation but as part of an integrated strategy. Concrete options include combining income protection with investments in renewable energy communities and sustainable public transport grids, which simultaneously reduce costs, cut emissions, and expand equitable access.

02.

Prioritize **Strategic Targeting of Vulnerable Populations.**

Evidence suggest, that focused interventions deliver superior distributional results compared to universal approaches. Portugal's targeted strategy concentrated most efficiency measures on vulnerable consumers. At the same time, increases in social protection expenditure have been shown to reduce energy poverty and remain resilient during crises. Carbon tax revenue recycling through tax cuts and rebates has improved consumption shares for lower-income households. Research shows that lump-sum transfers work better for lower incomes, while tax reductions—especially labor taxes—benefit higher incomes, while tax reductions benefit higher incomes (Köppl, A., & Schratzenstaller, M., 2023). By contrast, universal subsidies and across-the-board tax cuts often fail to benefit those most in need (Kyprianou et al., 2019; Brzezinski & Kaczan, 2025; Rodríguez-Alvarez et al., 2021)

In practice, this requires establishing clear and transparent criteria that allow support to be directed precisely to those most affected. Instead of dispersing resources through broad, universal measures, policy design should be guided by indicators of vulnerability that combine social, territorial, and energy-use dimensions. It is crucial to distinguish between universal entitlements, such as social protection systems, which are accessible to all but progressive in their redistributive effect, and untargeted subsidies like across-the-board price cuts, which tend to be regressive. Embedding these criteria in both the planning and delivery of programs certify that assistance reaches the households most in need, enhancing both effectiveness and fairness.

Policy recommendations

03.

Address **Multiple Dimensions of Inequality**.

Policy impacts extend far beyond income to encompass skill-based, geographic, gender, and demographic inequalities. Energy price increases have been shown to reduce female employment rates while leaving male employment unaffected, driven by occupational segregation and lower geographic mobility. Climate policies have tended to favor technicians while disadvantaging manual workers. Rural households have faced disproportionate burdens from carbon pricing compared to urban populations (Curuk et al., 2025; Wier et al., 2005; Feng et al., 2010; Marin & Vona, 2019).

Implementing this recommendation requires systematically assessing how policies affect different groups before they are enacted. This involves conducting distributional analyses that consider gender, geography, occupation, and household structure, and then adapting measures to mitigate identified inequalities. Examples include tailoring eligibility rules, introducing compensatory mechanisms, or linking climate measures with labor market support. Transparent reporting of these differentiated impacts is essential to maintain public legitimacy and to ensure that the transition is perceived as equitable rather than exclusionary.

The effectiveness of policies depends on **careful attention to the multidimensional, interconnected nature of climate vulnerabilities** and the imperative of ensuring that no one is left behind in Europe's transition toward **Sustainable Human Development**.

04.

Address **Structural Misalignments**.

Effective policy implementation requires identifying and addressing fundamental structural misalignments that prevent vulnerable populations from accessing support. National experiences show that coordination failures between agencies, definitional mismatches across regulations, misaligned incentives between property owners and tenants, and fragmented territorial governance have all undermined policy effectiveness (Seebauer et al., 2019).

Addressing these misalignments requires establishing mechanisms that enforce coordination across actors and governance levels. Clear and consistent definitions must be developed to prevent gaps in coverage, while frameworks should be designed to align the incentives of tenants and providers. Harmonising rules across territories is also essential to avoid fragmented outcomes where access to benefits depends on location. Importantly, overcoming institutional barriers is key to scaling renewable energy communities and sustainable public transport grids, ensuring that such innovations are not confined to advantaged regions. Energy communities in particular exemplify how democratizing access to clean energy can reduce costs for vulnerable households while addressing entrenched asymmetries of power between consumers and large providers.

Embedding accountability and conflict-resolution mechanisms from the outset ensures that well-intentioned policies translate into tangible improvements for those they are meant to reach.

References & other info

- Brzezinski, M., & Kaczan, M. (2025). [*Carbon taxes in Europe do not hurt the poor: Evidence from existing taxation schemes.*](#) Ecological Economics, 233, 108585.
- Curuk, M., Rozendaal, R., & Wendler, T. (2025). [*Gender differences in the employment effects of climate policy.*](#) Energy Economics, 145, 108394.
- Feng, K., Hubacek, K., Guan, D., Contestabile, M., Minx, J., & Barrett, J. (2010). [*Distributional effects of climate change taxation: The case of the UK.*](#) Environmental Science & Technology, 44(10), 3670–3676.
- Krstić, G., Vladislavljević, M., Vuksanović, N. and Žarković, J. (2024). [*European energy divide: exploring determinants and dynamics of energy poverty.*](#) SPES Working paper no. 6.1, SPES project – Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios. Florence: University of Florence. Available at <https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/publications-deliverables/>
- Köppl, A., & Schratzenstaller, M. (2023). [*Carbon taxation: A review of the empirical literature.*](#) Journal of Economic Surveys, 37(4), 1353–1388
- Kyprianou, I., Serghides, D. K., Varo, A., Gouveia, J. P., Kopeva, D., & Murauskaite, I. (2019). [*Energy poverty policies and measures in 5 EU countries: A comparative study.*](#) Energy and Buildings, 196, 46–60.

-
- Marin, G., & Vona, F. (2019). [*Climate policies and skill-biased employment dynamics: Evidence from EU countries.*](#) Journal of Environmental Economics and Management, 98, 102253.
 - Palencia-Esteban, A., Brunori, P., (2025). [*Vulnerabilities in Europe During Times of Transition.*](#) SPES Working Paper no. 6.2, SPES project – Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios. Florence: University of Florence. Available at: <https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/publications-deliverables>
 - Rodríguez-Alvarez, A., Llorca, M., & Jamasb, T. (2021). [*Alleviating energy poverty in Europe: Front-runners and laggards.*](#) Energy Economics, 103, 105575.
 - Seebauer, S., Friesenecker, M., & Einfeld, K. (2019). [*Integrating climate and social housing policy to alleviate energy poverty: an analysis of targets and instruments in Austria.*](#) Energy Sources, Part B, 14(7–9), 304–326.
 - Wier, M., Lenzen, M., Munksgaard, J., & Smed, S. (2005). [*Effects of household consumption patterns on CO2 requirements.*](#) Economic Systems Research, 17(3), 259–274

This Policy Brief was written by

María José Cota Salgado, London School of Economics and Political Science;
Nora Waitkus, London School of Economics and Political Science.

Contributors and peer reviewers

Mario Biggeri, University of Florence; Paolo Brunori, London School of Economics and Political Science; Jacopo Cammeo, European University Institute; Filippo Cuccaro, University of Florence; Andrea Ferrannini, University of Florence; Amaia Palencia-Esteban, London School of Economics and Political Science; Katja Reuter, Social Platform; Jelena Žarković, University of Belgrade.

Disclaimer

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

This document reflects the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Funded by European Union's Horizon
Europe Programme under Grant
Agreement No. 101094551

Sustainability
performances,
evidence & scenarios